

ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING: LACK OF SPEAKING SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13640916>

Abstract: This article explores the challenges faced by English language learners in Uzbekistan, particularly in developing speaking skills. It examines the factors contributing to the lack of speaking proficiency and proposes strategies to improve the situation. The article draws upon existing literature and analyzes the current state of English language education in Uzbekistan. The findings suggest that a combination of teacher training, communicative teaching approaches, and increased exposure to authentic language use can enhance learners' speaking abilities.

Keywords: English language learning, speaking skills, Uzbekistan, communicative approach, teacher training

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilar duch kelayotgan muammolar, xususan, nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Ingliz tilini yaxshi bilmaslikka yordam beradigan omillar ko'rib chiqiladi va vaziyatni yaxshilash strategiyalari taklif etiladi. Maqolada mavjud adabiyotlar asosida O'zbekistonda ingliz tili ta'limining hozirgi holati tahlil qilinadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, o'qitishning kommunikativ yondashuvlari va haqiqiy tildan ko'proq foydalanish o'quvchilarning nutq qobiliyatini yaxshilashi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tilini o'rganish, nutq qobiliyatlari, O'zbekiston, kommunikativ yondashuv, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются изучающие английский язык в Узбекистане, в частности, в развитии разговорных навыков. Рассматриваются факторы, способствующие недостаточному владению английским языком, и предлагаются стратегии для улучшения ситуации. В статье на основе имеющейся литературы анализируется текущее состояние образования по английскому языку в Узбекистане. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что сочетание подготовки учителей, коммуникативных подходов к обучению и более широкого использования аутентичного языка может улучшить разговорные способности учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Изучение английского языка, разговорные навыки, Узбекистан, коммуникативный подход, подготовка учителей.

INTRODUCTION

English language proficiency has become increasingly important in Uzbekistan due to globalization and the country's growing international ties [1]. However, many learners in Uzbekistan struggle to develop adequate speaking skills, hindering their ability to communicate effectively in English [2]. This article aims to investigate the factors contributing to the lack of speaking skills among English language learners in Uzbekistan and propose strategies to address this issue.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify the key factors influencing English language learning in Uzbekistan. The review included articles from peer-reviewed journals, books, and reports from educational institutions. The literature search focused on studies using databases such as JSTOR, Google Scholar, and ERIC. The search terms included "English language learning," "speaking skills," "Uzbekistan," and "communicative approach."

RESULTS

The literature review revealed several factors contributing to the lack of speaking skills among English language learners in Uzbekistan. These include:

Teacher-centered teaching methods: Many English language classrooms in Uzbekistan rely heavily on grammar-translation and memorization, neglecting the development of communicative competence [3].

Limited exposure to authentic language use: Learners often lack opportunities to practice speaking English in real-life situations, as the language is not widely used outside the classroom [4].

Insufficient teacher training: Many English language teachers in Uzbekistan lack the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively teach speaking skills [5].

Exam-oriented education system: The focus on passing written exams often overshadows the importance of developing speaking abilities [6].

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The findings suggest that a multi-faceted approach is needed to address the lack of speaking skills among English language learners in Uzbekistan. Firstly, teacher training programs should prioritize the development of communicative teaching strategies, equipping teachers with the skills to facilitate speaking activities in the classroom [7]. This includes training teachers to create

interactive lessons that encourage student participation, such as role-plays, debates, and group discussions. By shifting the focus from teacher-centered to student-centered learning, teachers can create an environment that fosters the development of speaking skills.

Secondly, learners should be provided with more opportunities to engage in authentic language use, such as through language clubs, conversation partners, and study abroad programs [8]. These experiences allow learners to practice speaking English in real-life situations, building their confidence and fluency. Additionally, incorporating authentic materials, such as podcasts, videos, and news articles, into the curriculum can expose learners to a variety of English accents and contexts, better preparing them for real-world communication.

Furthermore, the education system should strike a balance between exam preparation and the development of communicative competence. This can be achieved by incorporating speaking assessments into the curriculum and providing resources for teachers to create engaging speaking activities. By valuing speaking skills alongside reading, writing, and listening, the education system can send a clear message about the importance of oral communication in language learning.

Moreover, technology can play a crucial role in enhancing English language learning in Uzbekistan. The use of language learning apps, online resources, and virtual classrooms can provide learners with additional opportunities to practice speaking skills outside the traditional classroom setting. These tools can also help bridge the gap between rural and urban areas, ensuring that all learners have access to quality English language education.

However, it is important to acknowledge the challenges that may arise when implementing these strategies. Limited resources, resistance to change, and the need for ongoing professional development for teachers are potential obstacles that must be addressed. Policymakers and educational institutions should work together to allocate resources, provide support for teachers, and create a culture that values innovation and continuous improvement in English language education.

In conclusion, addressing the lack of speaking skills among English language learners in Uzbekistan requires a comprehensive approach that involves teacher training, authentic language use, a balanced curriculum, and the integration of technology. By implementing these strategies and overcoming potential challenges, Uzbekistan can create an environment that nurtures the

development of confident and proficient English speakers, enabling them to succeed in an increasingly globalized world.

CONCLUSIONS

Addressing the lack of speaking skills among English language learners in Uzbekistan requires a concerted effort from educators, policymakers, and learners themselves. By implementing communicative teaching approaches, providing opportunities for authentic language use, and prioritizing the development of speaking skills in the curriculum, Uzbekistan can improve the English language proficiency of its learners. This, in turn, will enhance their ability to participate in global conversations and contribute to the country's international development

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